

RELATIONSHIP OF INTERFACE FRACTURE ENERGY AND INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE UNDER HYDROTHERMAL TREATMENT

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Abstract: The mechanical and physical properties of composite materials are greatly influenced by the structure and properties of fiber/matrix interface. Short beam shear test is often performed to evaluate the laminar interface properties in real applications, especially for studying them after a given hydrothermal treatment. However, the results depend on the interface and the matrix properties, so the degradation mechanism of composite under hydrothermal condition is difficult to analyze only based on the short beam shear test. In this study, carbon fiber/epoxy resin interface properties, quantified by means of interface fracture energy, are tested in various hydrothermal conditions, such as hygroscopic treatments, re-drying treatment, temperature from 25°C to 130°C and 130°C after hygroscopic treatment. In addition, to analyze the relationship of interface properties measured by micro-mechanical and macro methods, short beam shear tests are simultaneously performed in the same treatments. The results show that interface fracture energy degrades obviously after hygroscopic treatments rather than under high temperature, while the degradation degree of interlaminar shear strength is more sensitive to temperature. Moreover, interlaminar shear strength for studied composite under various treatments largely depends on the mechanics property of matrix than interface property.

1. Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites are widely used for aircraft structure materials due to their light weight and high performance [1-2]. Otherwise, composites in the service of aircraft structure are usually exposure to the wet and thermal conditions. And the degradation of fiber, matrix, and fiber/matrix interface is caused by moisture absorption and temperature increasing. The mechanical properties of composite, especially the transverse properties, are significantly influenced by the variations of fiber/matrix interface undergoes hygroscopic and temperature deterioration [3].

Therefore, researches have paid more attention to the moisture effect on the fiber/matrix interface. One of the conventional methods to measure the interface shear strength is short beam shear test, which is also applied for evaluation of fiber/matrix interface property after a given hydrothermal treatment [4-6]. However, it is difficult to eliminate the influence of the matrix and fiber properties on the interlaminar shear strength derived from short beam test. Many micro-mechanic methods are developed to directly study the fiber/matrix interface properties. Most of these techniques are hardly used for characterization of the interface properties vs. moisture absorption content and temperature due to microscale dimension and complicated preparation for testing sample

except single fiber fragmentation test (SFFT). The SFFT specimens typically involve a single or a few parallel fibers embedded in the center of a matrix coupon, which is convenient for hydroscopic and high temperature treatments [7-8].

A stress-based model deduced from Kelly-Tyson model [9] requires a high break strain of the matrix (three times than of the fiber). However, the resin used in aircraft structure with the elongation range from 3% to 4% dissatisfies the requirement above, while the break strain of carbon fiber is about 1.5-2.1%. Therefore, we introduced an energy-based model in this work which was first proposed by Wagner et al [10-11]. For this method, interface fracture energy (Γ_i), a parameter denoting the interface bonding property, can be obtained at the first fiber break, which is fit for the evaluation of the interphase in brittle resin matrix composites. Γ_i is calculated as follow:

$$\Gamma_i = \frac{\sigma_{f\infty}^2 r_f}{2E_f L_d} \left[\frac{L_d}{2} + \frac{1}{\beta} - \frac{\beta E_f r_f^2}{16G_f} \right] - \frac{r_f \Gamma_f}{2L_d} \quad (1)$$

$$\beta = \frac{1}{r_f} \sqrt{\frac{2G_m}{E_f \ln(r_m/r_f)}} \quad (2)$$

where E_f is the fiber Young's modulus, $\sigma_{f\infty}$ is the far field fiber stress, L_d is the interfacial debonding length, Γ_i is fiber fracture energy, r_f is the fiber radius, r_m is the effective radius of the matrix, G_f and G_m are the shear modulus of fiber and matrix, respectively. $\sigma_{f\infty}$ is along the fiber axial and consisted of four kinds of stresses for SFFT specimen, i.e. applied tensile stress σ_f , thermal residual stress σ_{th} , imposed pre-stress σ_{pre} and moisture expanding stress σ_{hy} . And it is expressed as follow:

$$\sigma_{f\infty} = \sigma_f - \sigma_{th} + \sigma_{pre} + \sigma_{hy} \quad (3)$$

The aim of this study is to find out the relationship of interface fracture energy (from SFFT test) and interlaminar shear strength (from short-beam shear test) of carbon fiber reinforced high-temperature cured epoxy resin in various hydrothermal conditions.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

T300 carbon fiber (Toray Inc.) and a high-temperature cured epoxy resin (named 5228), used for SFFT specimens preparation, were supplied by Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials (BIAM). This epoxy resin was cured for 1h at 130°C, 2h at 180°C, and 3h at 190°C. The properties of carbon fiber and epoxy resin including the parameters used in the energy-based model are listed in Table1. The unidirectional laminates for short beam shear test, manufactured with T300 and 5228 epoxy resin system prepreg, were also supplied by BIAM.

Table 1 Properties of T300 carbon fiber and epoxy resin

Parameters	T300	Epoxy resin
Tensile strength σ (MPa)	3500	86
Young's modulus E (GPa)	230	3.5
Poisson's ratio μ	0.2	0.35
Fracture energy Γ (J/m ²)	10	—
Fiber radius r_f (μ m)	3.5	—
Effective radius of matrix r_m (μ m)	—	42
CTE α (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	-0.5	65

2.2 Hydrothermal treatments

The hydrothermal treatments for both SFFT test and short beam test specimen included immersion to deionized water at 70°C for 7d and at 100°C for 3d, and their re-drying treatments at 70°C for 7d in oven, test temperature from 25°C to 130°C and 130°C after boiling water immersion for 3d. The test temperature was controlled by the environment chambers.

2.3 Single fiber fragmentation test (SFFT)

A single T300 carbon fiber was carefully embedded in the epoxy resin system and the SFFT specimens were prepared according to the resin cure schedule. A polish process was performed after curing to facilitate the observation of debonding region. Then, the SFFT specimen was fixed to a self-made SFFT

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apparatus (shown in Fig.1) and tensioned by the tensile tester with the crosshead speed of 0.0076mm/s. The initiation fiber break and the birefringence image were observed by the polarizing microscope, and the pictures were collected through a digital camera. σ_f and L_d were directly measured from the SFFT apparatus while the resin tensile modulus E_m in various hydrothermal conditions was obtained from stress-strain curve.

Fig.1 Sketch of SFFT apparatus

Table2 Values of E_m , Γ_i and ILSS under different hydrothermal conditions

Hydrothermal conditions	Test temperature	E_m /GPa	Γ_i /J•m ⁻²	ILSS/MPa
Dry	25°C	2.39(0.08) ^a	1535(177)	97.9(3.3)
70 °C water immersion 7d	25°C	2.26(0.10)	672(69)	85.7(6.4)
Boiling water immersion 3d	25°C	2.14(0.07)	480(104)	83.4(3.1)
Re-drying after 70°C water immersion 7d	25°C	2.59(0.06)	1513(263)	98.5(3.4)
Re-drying after boiling water immersion 3d	25°C	2.67(0.10)	969(133)	93.4(2.5)
Dry	50°C	2.09(0.09)	1136(207)	79.9(3.6)
Dry	80°C	1.99(0.08)	1014(96)	70.1(2.7)
Dry	110°C	1.89(0.06)	991(113)	58.7(3.8)
Dry	130°C	1.78(0.09)	1025(170)	52.5(4.6)
Boiling water immersion 3d	130°C	1.25(0.07)	140(54)	37.9(1.5)

a Standard deviation

As seen in Table2, E_m , Γ_i and ILSS decrease after water absorption and test temperature increasing. The values decline markedly when specimen exposure to wet and hot conditions. After re-drying treatment of 70 °C water immersion 7d, Γ_i basically returns to the dry specimen level and E_m and ILSS even exceed the value of dry condition. Otherwise, for the specimen experiences the condition of

2.4 Interlaminar shear strength test (ILSS)

The test coupons of uniform size were cut from the panel for mechanical characterization. Interlaminar shear strengths (ILSS) testing were conducted on an Instron 5565 test apparatus using three point bending according to ASTM D2344. The test was performed as a testing speed of 1mm/min. The dimensions of the sample were 20×6×2mm.

3. Results and discussion

The interface fracture energy and interlaminar shear strength under various hygroscopic conditions, temperature from 25°C to 130°C and testing at 130°C after boiling water immersion 3d were investigated. Additionally, the mechanical properties of epoxy resin (tensile modulus) under the same treatments were measured from tensile tester machine when the SFFT test performed. All the values of E_m , Γ_i and ILSS are shown in Table2.

re-drying after boiling water immersion 3d, only E_m recovers, and both Γ_i and ILSS are incompletely recovery. The trends of degradation of the three performances are different in various hydrothermal treatments. The property retentions referred to the case in dry condition are given in Fig.2-4. In order to study the relationship interface properties from SFFT test and ILSS from short beam shear test, the

retention of E_m , Γ_i and ILSS at different hydrothermal conditions are shown in Fig.2, Fig.3 and Fig.4, respectively.

Fig.2 Retention of interface fracture energy, interlaminar shear strength and modulus of 5228 resin under different hygroscopic treatments

In Fig.2, Γ_i degrades more obviously than E_m and ILSS when specimens are exposure to 70°C water immersion and boiling water immersion. The decline degree of E_m and ILSS is similar after water aging. It indicates that interface fracture energy is more sensitive to moisture absorption. After experiencing re-drying treatments after boiling water 3d, the values of Γ_i and ILSS are unable to recover to the dry condition level, revealing an irreversible change. Moreover, the reason of incompletely recovery of ILSS may ascribe to the irreversible process of interface property.

Fig.3 Retention of interface fracture energy, interlaminar shear strength and modulus of 5228 resin from 25°C to 130°C

Fig.3 shows the variation of E_m , Γ_i and ILSS as function of temperature. As the temperature increasing, E_m and ILSS progressively decrease and Γ_i is trend to reach a plateau after 80°C. It is demonstrated that interface fracture energy is insensitive to temperature comparing to E_m and ILSS.

Fig.4 Retention of interface fracture energy, interlaminar shear strength and modulus of 5228 resin under different hydrothermal treatments

The test at 130°C after boiling water 3d was performed to investigate the coupling influence of moisture and temperature on the property of E_m , Γ_i and ILSS. For the purpose, the conditions of testing at 130°C and boiling water 3d are given as reference. As shown in Fig.4, the degradations of E_m , Γ_i and ILSS under the condition of testing at 130°C after boiling water 3d are almost equal to the sum of the cases under 130°C and boiling water 3d. Comparing the degradation degree in these four conditions, the trends of E_m and ILSS are still close. In general, from Fig.2 to Fig.4, we deduce that interlaminar shear strength of T300/5228 composite greatly depends on the resin mechanical property rather than interface property under hygroscopic and high temperature treatments.

4. Conclusion

Both interface fracture energy and interlaminar shear strength for T300/5228 composite decrease under the effect of moisture and temperature. The degradation in the condition of testing at 130°C after boiling

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water 3d is nearly an accumulation effect of moisture and temperature. Additionally, interface fracture energy is sensitively affected by hygroscopic conditions rather than temperature. To the contrary, interlaminar shear strength is susceptible to temperature. Moreover, interlaminar shear strength for T300/5228 composite under various treatments depends on both matrix and interface property, mostly relates to matrix mechanical property.

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